

1 **An empirical study of the wound effect on sap flux density measured with**
2 **thermal dissipation probes**

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20 **KEYWORDS**

21 sap flow, sap velocity, heat transfer, wound healing reaction, sap flow underestimations, European beech,
22 *Fagus sylvatica*, sessile oak, *Quercus petraea*

23
24 Running head: WOUND EFFECT ON SAP FLUX BY THERMAL DISSIPATION

25 **SUMMARY**

26 This study investigates empirically, for first time, the wound effect on sap flux densities measured with
27 thermal dissipation probes. We found that the wound formation around inserted sensors is one of the largest
28 biases for this method. However, a practical approach is proposed to correct direct field observations and
29 hence achieve more accurate sap flux density estimations with thermal dissipation probes.

30

31 **ABSTRACT**

32 The insertion of thermal dissipation (TD) sensors on tree stems for sap flux density (SFD) measurements
33 can lead to SFD underestimations due to a wound formation close to the drill hole. However, the wound
34 effect has not been assessed experimentally for this method yet. Here, we propose an empirical approach to
35 investigate for the effect of the wound healing on measured sap flux with TD probes. The approach was
36 performed for both, diffuse-porous (*Fagus sylvatica*) and ring-porous (*Quercus petraea*) species. TD probes
37 were installed on different dates along the growing season to document the effects of the dynamic wound
38 formation. The trees were cut in autumn and additional sensors were installed in the cut stems, therefore,
39 without potential effects of wound development. A range of water pressures were applied to the stem
40 segments and SFDs were simultaneously measured by TD sensors as well as gravimetrically in the
41 laboratory. The formation of wounds around sensors installed in living tree stems lead to underestimation
42 of sap flux density by $21.4\% \pm 3\%$ and $47.5\% \pm 3.8\%$ in beech and oak, respectively. The differences
43 between SFD underestimations of diffuse-porous beech and ring-porous oak were, however, not statistically
44 significant. Sensors with 5, 11 and 22 week old wounds showed also no significant differences, which
45 implies that the influence of wound formation on SFD estimates was completed within the first weeks after
46 perforation. These results were confirmed by time courses of SFD measurements in the field. Field SFD
47 values decreased immediately after sensor installation and reached stable values after about two weeks with
48 similar underestimations to the ones observed in the lab. We therefore propose a feasible approach to correct
49 directly field observations of sap flux density for potential underestimations due to the wound effect.

50

51

52 1. INTRODUCTION

53 The thermal dissipation method (TD) developed by Granier (1985, 1987), has become one of the most
54 widespread methods for determination of tree transpiration, due to low costs and the easily comprehensible
55 sensor construction (Davis et al. 2012). This is especially advantageous for studies focused on the estimation
56 of water balances (Schäfer et al. 2002, Holst et al. 2010) or partitioning of evapotranspiration (ET) at the
57 stand level (Herbst et al. 2007, 2008, Oishi et al. 2010, Clausnitzer et al. 2011, Gebauer et al. 2012,
58 Ringgaard et al. 2012), where a large number of sensors are needed. However, numerous studies report
59 considerable errors using the TD method (Bush et al. 2010, Hultine et al. 2010, Sun et al. 2011, Reyes-
60 Acosta et al. 2012, Paudel et al. 2013), which gave the largest underestimations in comparison to other
61 methods (Steppe et al. 2010). Some sources of uncertainty have been frequently described, such as the great
62 spatial variability of sap flux density within species (i.e., circumferential variability, Saveyn et al. 2008, and
63 radial variability, (Ford et al. 2004, Gebauer et al. 2008) and between species (e.g., Sun et al. 2011), bad
64 positioning of the sensor probes (Clearwater et al. 1999, Shin`ichi & Tadashi 2010), inadequate
65 determination of the ΔT_0 (see below) parameter (Wullschleger et al. 2011, Vergeynst et al. 2014), and
66 systematic errors due to the lack of species-specific calibrations (Lu et al. 2004, Bush et al. 2010).
67 Substantial effort has been given in the improvements on accuracy of the TD method but a large fraction of
68 the sap flux density remains still underestimated by this method (Steppe et al. 2010) and the specific causes
69 remain unclear.

70
71 The wound formation in response to sensor insertion into the xylem has been suggested as one of the largest
72 sources of error in the sap flux density estimation with TD sensors (Steppe et al. 2010, Wullschleger et al.
73 2011), although no experimental study has tested this hypothesis yet. The TD sensors consist of two probes
74 of stainless steel equipped with thermocouple junctions that are inserted within the tree stem, usually within
75 previously inserted aluminium tubes of 20 mm length and 2 mm diameter. The upper probe is constantly
76 heated whereas the lower sensor acts as a reference, and the temperature difference between the two probes
77 (ΔT) is used to calculate sap flux density (SFD) with an empirical function (Granier 1985). The insertion of
78 TD probes within the sapwood represents, therefore, an unavoidable disturbance of the conductive tissue
79 surrounding the measurement point. The first direct and immediate vessel disruption, consequent air
80 embolism and the interruption of water flux around the drilled holes (Dujesiefken et al. 1999) may cause an
81 inherent measurement error to all invasive methods. This error is, nonetheless, accounted as long as the
82 method is calibrated under similar conditions. More problematic is the indirect and later effect associated to
83 the wounding reaction of the wood tissue close to the damaged area. This reaction was already described by
84 the CODIT principle (Compartmentalization Of Damage In Trees, Shigo 1984, Liese & Dujesiefken 1996,
85 Dujesiefken et al. 2005). According to that principle, the damaged sap wood tissue is actively isolated from
86 the healthy one by sealing the water conduction elements and structural components in order to encapsulate

87 spreading fungi and prevent the cavitation in the affected vessels. Hence, a tissue die back of parenchyma
88 cells occurs after air embolism, followed by the formation of a reaction zone surrounding the wound, the so
89 called compartmentalization. This reaction zone, detectable as a discoloration of sapwood, is characterized
90 by the closure of vessels, phenols accumulation and changes in wood properties, with the consequent
91 reduction in its conductive capacity and the alteration of the heat transport. Since the TD method is based
92 on the heat conductivity of the wood, the alteration of this property associated to the wounding reaction can
93 bias SFD estimations systematically.

94

95 Potential alterations in wood thermal and physical properties stemming from an active wounding reaction
96 are not included in the standard TD calibration equation. Granier's (1985, 1987) empirical equation was
97 developed using TD sensors that were installed after cutting the stem segments and, therefore, an active
98 compartmentalization and wound formation did not occur. Empirical validations on wound-affected sensors
99 are then imperative to accurately describe the effects of wood physical and anatomical alterations on the
100 measured sap flux density. The effect of the wound effect on SFD estimates was, however, never studied
101 up to now despite the wide recognition of this effect, for example for the heat pulse method (Cohen et al.
102 1981, Swanson & Whitfield 1981). The magnitude of errors, its dynamics and time frame as well as potential
103 effects of different species, phenology or environmental factors are also completely unknown. The main
104 objectives of this study were firstly to determine experimentally the magnitude of sap flux density
105 underestimation associated with wound formation, and secondly, to develop an approach to account for the
106 wound effect on TD measurements in the field. Therefore, sets of TD probes were installed at different dates
107 along the growing season in diffuse- and ring-porous trees (*Fagus sylvatica* and *Quercus petraea*). At the
108 end of the growing season, the trees were cut and additional sets of sensors were installed in each stem
109 segment after logging ("After Cut", AC). We compared sap flux density measured by sensors installed in
110 living trees with AC sensors and the gravimetric reference observations in the laboratory. We expected a
111 better performance of AC sensors, while higher underestimations on probes installed in living trees. We
112 also hypothesized larger underestimations in earlier installed probes and in ring-porous species.

113

114 **2. MATERIAL AND METHODS**

115 *2.1. Plant material and study site*

116 Trees of this study are located in a mixed deciduous forest (Leinefelde, Thüringen, Germany, 51° 20' 13''
117 N, 10° 22' 07'' E, and 450 m asl). Climate in the study area is subatlantic-submontane with an annual mean
118 temperature of 8.2 °C and an annual mean precipitation of 577 mm (2003-2014, O. Kolle, Max Planck
119 Institute for Biogeochemistry, Jena, personal communication). The forest is relatively homogenous and
120 composed by even-aged stands where European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) is the dominant species (97% of
121 relative abundance) with accompanying sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*, 3%). Tree height and diameter at

122 breast height were 33 m (standard deviation: 7.2 m) and 44 cm (standard deviation: 12.4 cm), respectively
123 (2012, M. Mund, Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, Jena, personal communication).

124
125 Two beech trees (diffuse-porous) and two oak trees (ring-porous) were selected for this experiment, so that
126 the effect of wound formation could be investigated on species of different xylem anatomy (Table 1). For
127 that, trees with regular concentric growth, no evidences of knots, scars, diseases or irregularities in the stem
128 surface were chosen.

129

130 2.2. Thermal dissipation method

131 The TD sensors used in this study were constructed manually according to Davis et al. (2012) and the
132 specifications of the original design of Granier (1985). Each sensor consisted of two probes of 20 mm length
133 and 1.1 mm diameter stainless steel needles and a T-type thermocouple (copper-constantan). Thermocouples
134 were made by using copper wire of 0.10 mm diameter (Reichelt Elektronik, Germany) and fine gauge of
135 constantan wire insulated with Teflon with a diameter of 0.13 mm, (OMEGA Newport Electronics GmbH,
136 Germany). Both wires were connected using a commercial tin solder. The upper probe of each sensor was
137 continuously heated at constant power (0.2 W) whereas the lower probe was not heated and measured the
138 ambient temperature of the wood tissue. The constantan ends of the two thermocouples were connected to
139 measure the temperature difference (ΔT) between the probes. The temperature difference was measured
140 every 60 s and the average of 10 min was recorded on a data-logger (CR1000, Campbell Scientific, Logan,
141 UT, USA) and two multiplexers (AM16/32, Campbell Scientific, Logan, UT, USA).

142
143 ΔT is then related to the sap flux density (SFD, $\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$) using the empirical equation developed by
144 Granier (1985):

$$145 \quad SFD = 0.0119 * K^{1.231} \quad (1)$$

146 where 0.0119 and 1.231 are empirically determined coefficients and K is a dimensionless value defined as:

$$147 \quad K = \frac{\Delta T_0 - \Delta T}{\Delta T} \quad (2)$$

148 ΔT_0 is the value of ΔT obtained under zero flow conditions or the maximum temperature difference between
149 the two needles and ΔT is the measured temperature difference at a given sap flux density. This empirical
150 formula was developed by Granier (1985, 1987) for measuring sap flux density in trees of stem diameter
151 > 40 mm. It was initially established experimentally from measurements on two conifers [*Pseudotsuga*
152 *menziesii* (Mirb.) Franco and *Pinus nigra* (Arnold)] and one ring-porous hardwood species (*Quercus*
153 *pedunculata* Ehrh.), providing an independent relationship between K and SFD on the three species
154 studied. The equation depends on the heat field created by the heated probe and, therefore, on the
155 particular physical properties of wood and probes and on the quantity of heat applied. Since the

156 empirical calibration has little physical basis (Smith and Allen 1996; Clearwater et al. 1999) a
157 recalibration is needed in those cases in which any of the factors is modified. The hand made sensors
158 used in this study were previously tested against commercially available sensors (Type SF-, Ecomatik,
159 Germany) in order to prove their accuracy and reliability (results not shown).

160

161 *2.3. Field experimental setup*

162 Six sets of TD sensors were installed at different dates in the growing season (DOY 134, 208 and 253;
163 spring, summer and fall sensors, respectively) in each of the selected trees in the field. Sensors were equally
164 distributed in two 80 cm stem segments located at two heights (0.9-1.7 m and 2.2-3 m from the base). Hence,
165 each stem height contained three sensors per sampling date located at predefined positions around the stems,
166 so that each state of wound development would be present along the circumference. A minimum horizontal
167 distance of 20 cm and vertical distance of 40 cm was maintained between consecutive sensors and vertical
168 alignment was avoided to prevent thermal interferences. Stem diameters at the point of sensors insertion
169 ranged from 31.4 cm to 34.1 cm for beech and from 35.3 cm to 39.2 cm for oak (Table 1).

170

171 For sensor insertion, the bark was carefully removed at the point and two holes of 2 mm diameter, 2 cm
172 depths and 10 cm apart were drilled radially into the sapwood. A template was used in order to minimize
173 displacement errors during installation. Once the holes were drilled, an aluminium tube of 2 mm diameter
174 and 0.2 mm thick wall was inserted into each hole so that it was tightly fitted and completely immersed into
175 the wood (see Table 1 for details on sapwood depth of each stem segment). Sensor probes were then inserted
176 into each correspondent aluminium tube, which was previously filled with silicon grease to increase thermal
177 conductivity. Silicon grease was replaced periodically in order to prevent errors associated to silicon aging.
178 Finally, sensors were protected from damages and meteorological conditions and trees were wrapped with
179 aluminium foil to minimize possible interferences with natural temperature gradients (Do & Rocheteau
180 2002a, Lubczynski et al. 2012). Nonetheless, a pilot study showed that the natural temperature gradient
181 rarely exceeded 0.2 °C on the study site, so that this effect can be considered negligible (Do & Rocheteau
182 2002a).

183

184 Trees were logged just before the end of the growing season (DOY: 287), i.e. 22, 11 and 5 weeks after the
185 installations of spring, summer and fall sensors, respectively. The TD sensors were previously removed to
186 avoid damage during the logging operation, while the aluminum tubes remained within the stems,
187 encapsulated by the wounded areas. Two 80 cm long sections of each stem, including the preinstalled
188 aluminium tubes at all installation dates, were cut and wrapped in plastic foil to prevent desiccation and
189 carefully transported to the laboratory.

190
191 *2.4. Laboratory sap flux density measurements with gravimetric reference*
192 Once in the laboratory, the upper and the lower cut surfaces of the stem segments were previously recut
193 with a fine-tooth saw and visible blocked vessels were re-opened with a razor blade. Additional sensors
194 were installed (“After Cut”, AC) following the procedure described above. These measuring points are
195 considered as reference sensor measurements since the wound reaction is an active mechanism of defence
196 that involves hormone production and biochemical reactions (Shigo 1984). It is hence not expected to occur
197 in cut stems. The existing holes were also equipped again with randomly chosen TD Sensors. Therefore,
198 each segment contained a total of 12 sensors [3 sensors x (3 sampling dates + 1 AC)].

199
200 The whole segments were then erected in natural growth direction with their lower extremes immersed in
201 water (Fig. 1). A 2 cm strip of the bark was removed at the top of the stems to facilitate the installation of
202 an acrylic-plate. The airtight connection between plate and tree segment surface was achieved with a rubber
203 band and sealant. The valve in the middle of the plate was connected to a vacuum pump, which enabled the
204 application of different pressures (Fig. 1). The water passing through the cut stem segments was weighted
205 every 2 min using an electronic balance (model Europe 4000 AR, Gibertini, Novate Milanese, Germany,
206 accuracy of 0.01 g, for lower flux rates and model QS64B, Sartorius AG, Goettingen, Germany, accuracy
207 of 5 g, for higher flux rates). This setup was previously tested to check the absence of thermal interferences
208 between consecutive sensors by activating the heating alternatively on half of the sensors and checking the
209 temperature changes on the other half of non-heated sensors (Do & Rocheteau 2002b, Lubczynski et al.
210 2012).

211
212 The described experimental setup enabled the comparison of SFD measured by sensors installed in living
213 trees (i.e., with wound healing reaction: spring, summer, fall sensors) to the freshly installed sensors (i.e.,
214 without healing reaction: AC sensors) under the same flux density conditions. For that, constant pressures
215 were applied through the segments, resulting in a SFD of 0 to 25 cm³ cm⁻² h⁻¹ (gravimetric reference).
216 This range is within the magnitude reported in the literature (Granier 1985) and previously observed in the
217 field by sensor measurements. Sensors were shifted randomly to different measuring points in the stem
218 between each validation test to ensure that differences were not associated to possible sensor bias. The value
219 of ΔT_0 in Eq. 2 was determined as the maximum ΔT values that were recorded within a 24h period at zero
220 flow conditions. For this, stem segments were left partially immersed in water to ensure that the wood
221 tissue is rehydrated by capillary rise and to obtain a stable record of ΔT_0 (Fig. 1). Sensor SFD was calculated
222 according to Eq. (1) and (2). The gravimetric sap flux density, considered as the reference flux hereafter,
223 was calculated from the rate of change in the mass of water collected and normalized for the conducting
224 sapwood area.

225
226 The sapwood area of oak was determined visually at the end of the experiment by the change of color
227 between sapwood and heartwood. For beech, a 0.1% solution of methylene blue was dissolved in water and
228 sucked through the stem segments. Transversal slices were excised, photographed and the colored area was
229 quantified with the image processing software ImageJ (Schindelin et al. 2012).

230
231 Linear regressions were fitted to the gravimetric sap flux density values and the corresponding sensor
232 records, both for each date of installation and per tree species. Errors of the linear regression parameters
233 were calculated by bootstrapping the observations 1000 times. The same approach was followed when
234 comparing the pooled wound-affected measurements with AC results. The effect of the date of sensor
235 installation and the tree species on the relationship between TD sensor SFD estimates and gravimetrical
236 values were tested using analyses of the covariance (ANCOVA) with “species” or “date of installation” as
237 fixed factors and the gravimetrical sap flux as the covariate. Data were root-transformed to improve
238 normality and homoscedasticity. The same approach was used to explore the relationship between wound-
239 affected sensors and AC sensors.

240
241 Since linear regressions were not forced to have zero intercept, relative SFD underestimations and errors
242 vary depending on the sap flux range. For this reason, the differences between gravimetric flow and
243 estimates by TD sensors are expressed as the mean percentage of the gravimetric flux that is underestimated
244 by the TD sensors. For each mean measured value of gravimetric and sensor flux (data points in Figs. 3 and
245 4), the percentage of gravimetric SFD underestimated by TD sensors is calculated using the expression:

$$246 \quad \%SFD \text{ underestimated by TD} = \frac{SFD_{grav} - SFD_{sensor}}{SFD_{grav}} \times 100$$

247 where SFD_{grav} is the mean measured value of reference gravimetric flux and SFD_{sensor} is the mean
248 measured value by TD sensors. A similar expression was used to calculate the percentage of SFD
249 underestimated by TD sensors due to the wound effect only (Fig. 5):

$$250 \quad \%Wound \text{ effect SFD underestimation} = \frac{SFD_{sensor AC} - SFD_{sensor wounded}}{SFD_{sensor AC}} \times 100$$

251 where $SFD_{sensor AC}$ is the mean value of SFD measured by AC sensors and $SFD_{sensor wounded}$ is the mean
252 value of SFD measured by wound-affected sensors (i.e.: spring, summer and autumn sensors).

253 *2.5. Field data analysis*

254 Field data was evaluated to detect the progressive underestimations of SFD due to the wound development
 255 in living trees. Data from sensors with 10 weeks old wounds (spring sensors) were compared with data from
 256 sensors installed on the DOY 208 (summer sensors). Autumn sensors were not used for this comparison to
 257 avoid obscuring the results with leaf senescence at the end of the growing period. To reduce confounding
 258 effects of changing meteorological conditions, we selected periods of potentially similar transpiration.
 259 Vapor pressure deficit (VPD) and global radiation (R_g) were used to model non-water limited transpiration
 260 (PT) by combining a hyperbolic response curve of photosynthesis with the Ball-Berry-Leuning model of
 261 stomatal conductance, neglecting cuticular conductance (Leuning 1995, Berry & Roderick 2005):

$$262 \quad PT = \frac{a}{C_a} \frac{\alpha F_{GPP,sat} Q_{PPFD}}{F_{GPP,sat} + \alpha Q_{PPFD}} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{VPD} + \frac{1}{D_0}} \quad (3)$$

263 where $a = 9 \text{ Pa}(\text{air})^{-1}$ and $D_0 = 1 \text{ kPa}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ are empirical coefficients, C_a is the atmospheric CO_2 -
 264 concentration as an approximation of the concentration at the leaf surface ($400 \mu\text{mol}(\text{CO}_2) \text{ mol}(\text{air})^{-1}$),
 265 $F_{GPP,sat}$ is the gross primary productivity at saturated light intensity ($35.3 \mu\text{mol}(\text{CO}_2) \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), Q_{PPFD} is the
 266 measured photosynthetic photon flux density ($\text{mol}(\text{photons}) \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), α is the apparent quantum yield (0.099
 267 $\mu\text{mol}(\text{CO}_2) \text{ mol}(\text{photons})^{-1}$), and VPD is the vapor pressure deficit ($\text{kPa}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$). Specific values of the above
 268 constants are not relevant because PT is evaluated only relative to PT of DOY 209. Delayed responses of
 269 SFD to environmental drivers associated to tree water storage (Köstner et al. 1998, Burgess & Dawson
 270 2008) were avoided by selecting values measured from 10:00 h to 16:00 h when the highest daily flow rates
 271 usually occur. The average PT between 10:00 h and 16:00 h of DOY 209 plus a range of $0.09 \text{ mmol}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$
 272 $\text{m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ was used as a threshold to select days with comparable sap flow conditions. We report in the
 273 following mean values with standard errors.

274

275 3. RESULTS

276 3.1. Response of sap flux density to stepwise changes in flow rate

277 Figure 2 represents an example of the typical sensor responses in beech to stepwise changes in flux rates in
 278 response to different pumping pressures. SFD values from AC sensors were closer to the gravimetric
 279 reference, which indicates good performance of the self-made TD sensors using Granier's original
 280 calibration (Granier 1985). In contrast, all wound-affected sensors underestimated SFD compared to the
 281 gravimetric reference. In this particular case, the 5 weeks old fall sensors showed the smallest
 282 underestimations of all wound-affected sensors, which would be expected in case of a continuous
 283 degeneration of accuracy with time since installation. However, underestimations were not always larger in
 284 older wounds (cf. Fig. 3). Additionally, underestimation of SFD was also larger in absolute values at higher
 285 flow rates than at low flow rates.

286

287 Note that the suction-based verification system had to be interrupted periodically in order to empty the
288 Erlenmeyer flask, which is reflected as a drop in the SFD values between each pressure rate as well as in
289 the middle of the largest flow rate (700 mbar). Nonetheless, to ensure that the interruptions did not influence
290 the results, these values were not included in further analyses.

291 292 3.2. Validation of sap flux densities in cut stem segments

293 For each installation date, SFD measurements from sensors installed in each beech segment were averaged
294 for each pressure-step (34-108 sensor readings averaged per data point, depending on the duration of each
295 calibration step) and compared with the corresponding gravimetric reference (Fig. 3). Note that linear
296 regressions were not forced to have zero intercept, which implies that the SFD underestimations will vary
297 depending on the sap flux range. Freshly installed AC sensors were able to detect the highest proportion of
298 the gravimetric flux (mean of $86.1\% \pm 5.7\%$), whereas spring ($72.0\% \pm 4.7\%$), summer ($61.8\% \pm 3.9\%$) and
299 fall sensors ($58.0\% \pm 5.0\%$) underestimated the reference SFD values in similar magnitudes. The differences
300 between AC sensors and the rest of installation dates were significant ($P = 0.0002$), using an ANCOVA
301 with date of sensor installation as fixed factor and gravimetric sap flux as the covariate. Note that the mean
302 values are not simply the slopes in Figure 3 because they include the offsets.

303
304 Similar patterns were obtained in the case of oak (Fig. 4), where AC sensors were able to detect a higher
305 (ANCOVA, $P = 0.0015$) proportion of the flux ($72.0\% \pm 7.8\%$), compared to spring ($40.0\% \pm 5.1\%$),
306 summer ($52.6\% \pm 10.5\%$), and fall sensors ($30.8\% \pm 6.1\%$). Nonetheless, due to the very thin sapwood area
307 of one tree (0.54 cm), only two segments could be tested, which explains the larger uncertainty of the results.
308 This limitation was also reflected in larger intercepts and errors of the linear regressions.

309
310 Wound-affected sensors performed better in beech compared to oak, although differences were statistically
311 marginal and with a significant interaction of species with the gravimetric flux ($P = 0.046$, ANCOVA with
312 species as fixed factor and gravimetric sap flux as covariate). However, wound-free sensors have a similar
313 performance in both, beech and oak (ANCOVA, $P = 0.55$) with no significant interactions.

314
315 Since the date of installation did not exert a significant effect on the proportion of the sap flux density
316 detected by wound-affected sensors, the underestimations associated to wound formation were determined
317 by comparing all spring, summer and fall sensors simultaneously with sensors not affected by wounds (AC)
318 (Fig. 5). In beech, wound-affected sensors detected a mean of $78.6\% \pm 3.0\%$ of the flux density measured
319 by AC sensors. Therefore, the wound effect was responsible of about $21.4\% \pm 3.0\%$ of the total
320 underestimations from wounded sensors, with increasing values at higher sap flux densities (Fig.5a). In the
321 case of oak, only $52.5\% \pm 3.8\%$ of the wound-free SFD values were detected by wound-affected sensors.

322 Consequently, around $47.5\% \pm 3.8\%$ of the SFD was underestimated due to the wounding effect. An
323 ANCOVA with species as independent factor and sap flux from AC sensors as covariate showed, however,
324 that the seemingly large differences between beech and oak were not significant ($P = 0.13$), although the
325 interactions were significant.

326

327 *3.3. Circumferential variability of sap flux densities in stems*

328 An assessment of the circumferential variability of the sap flux density was performed to check for the
329 randomized location of sensors around the tree stem. Under the maximum gravimetric flow (beech: 23.3
330 $\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$; oak: $14.1 \text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$), sensor SFD ranged from 6 to $26.6 \text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$ for beech and 0.7 to
331 $14.7 \text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$ for oak. Fig. 6 shows that AC sensors were located in areas of both high as well as low
332 hydraulic conductivity. Moreover, AC sensors always detected higher SFD than wound-affected sensors in
333 both low conductive areas (e.g., beech 315°) and high conductive areas (e.g., beech 45°).

334

335 *3.4. Evaluation of the development of the wound effect in field data*

336 In order to evaluate the progressive development of the wound effect in living trees, we compared the sap
337 flux density from freshly installed sensors in beech trees (summer sensors installed on DOY 208) with the
338 sap flux density from wound-affected sensors that were installed 10 weeks earlier (spring sensors installed
339 on DOY 134). Only data of days with comparable potential transpiration rates were used to minimize
340 confounding meteorological effects on the detection of a potential drifting trend on recently installed
341 sensors. A total of 24 middays fulfilled the criterion $PT = 0.6 \pm 0.099 \text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Field SFD values from
342 sensors with 10 weeks-old wounds (spring sensors) were 22-47% lower than the ones from freshly installed
343 sensors (summer sensors) few days after their installation (Fig. 7). These values coincide with the
344 underestimation obtained from the lab experiment at similar sap flux density ranges (Fig. 5). As wounds
345 develop on the recently installed sensors, differences between summer and spring sensors decreased
346 progressively until they almost converged after 13 days. The differences between both sets of sensors
347 became stable two weeks after summer installation with ca. $7.5\% \pm 15.1\%$ lower flux densities on spring
348 sensors, which may be indicative of the advanced state of wound development on the most recently installed
349 sensors.

350

351 **4. DISCUSSION**

352 Despite the widespread use of the thermal dissipation method to study the ecophysiological responses of
353 tree transpiration, considerable measurement errors have been reported for this technique (Moore et al.
354 2010). Indeed, TD has been identified between several thermal methods as the one with the largest
355 uncertainty, both by empirical comparisons and by modeling studies (Tatarinov et al. 2005, Steppe et al.
356 2010). Several potential reasons have been suggested, but the real causes for the uncertainty remain

357 uncertain. Recent model simulations identified the wound formation in response to the sensor insertion as
358 one of the most important sources of errors for the TD technique (Wullschleger et al. 2011). No experimental
359 results were however available up to now to corroborate the contribution of the wound effect to TD
360 uncertainties and to provide insights into the mechanisms involved. This study provides, for the first time,
361 empirical information on the influence of the wounding process on the accuracy of the TD method. Results
362 presented here point to the wound healing reaction as one of the most important sources of error, which is
363 supported by consistent results from both field data and lab validation experiments. Concerns arise
364 immediately about the reliability of tree transpiration estimates based on TD measurements. The information
365 given in this paper allows us to design a strategy to correct field TD measurements and get an insight on the
366 magnitude of the potential underestimations associated to the wound reaction.

367

368 *4.1 Magnitude and characteristics of the wound effect on the TD method*

369 The wound effect, which happened on sensors installed on living tree stems, was responsible of around
370 21.4% and 47.5% SFD underestimation in beech and oak trees, respectively (Fig. 5), according to the lab
371 validation test. The same range of SFD underestimation (22%-47%) was also visible in the field during the
372 first 10 days on wound-affected sensors (Fig. 7). This source of error could explain, at least in part, the
373 progressive loss of accuracy frequently observed on long-term field measurements (Köstner et al. 1998,
374 Moore et al. 2010). The wound effect was indeed responsible for about two thirds of the total SFD
375 underestimations of wound-affected TD sensors when they were compared to the gravimetric reference
376 (Figs. 3 and 4). These findings raise serious doubts not only about the estimations of the ecosystem water
377 balance based on upscaled TD data, but also when determining the sensitivity of SFD to environmental
378 variables at the medium and long term.

379

380 The underestimations obtained here are well within published ranges from model simulations (Wullschleger
381 et al. 2011). However, model results led to over- and underestimations whereas the empirical results of this
382 study always showed SFD underestimations. A possible reason could be associated to the extension of the
383 wounded area beyond the perforation holes. The axial extension of the wounds observed here were $292 \pm$
384 33 mm^2 and $777 \pm 63 \text{ mm}^2$ for TD sensors inserted in oak and beech, respectively (Marañón-Jiménez et al.
385 2014), which are much larger than the values reported for the heat pulse velocity (HPV) method ($3.14\text{-}15.20$
386 mm^2) and used in the model simulations of Wullschleger et al. (2011). In this wounded area around the point
387 of probes insertion, the accumulation of gels, formation of tyloses and thickening of cell walls may obstruct
388 the conductive vessels (Zimmermann 1979, Rioux et al. 1998) thus reducing hydraulic conductivity and
389 heat transfer (Dimond et al. 1955, Sun et al. 2008, Collins et al. 2009, McElrone et al. 2010). Actually, TD
390 sensors also registered an increasing trend in night-time ΔT_0 values in the field (data not shown), likely as a
391 result of the progressive wound healing-isolation of TD sensors after their insertion. The extent of the

392 physical and anatomical transformations is indeed directly linked to a reduction of sensor performance
393 (Barrett et al. 1995, Wullschlegel et al. 2011). The application of a constant heat source by the heated probes
394 and the larger size of sensors in the TD method may lead to a more extensive wood physical transformation
395 compared to other heat transfer based techniques and hence to intensify the effects of the wound reaction
396 on sap flux density estimates.

397
398 In our experiment, AC sensors installed in cut stem segments, i.e. without wound reaction, measured about
399 14 to 28% lower flux densities than the gravimetric reference. This deviation fall within the range of
400 underestimations reported in other studies, such as 3%-27% (Reyes-Acosta et al. 2012), 14.3% (Häberle et
401 al. 2013), up to 50% (Hultine et al. 2010), and even 60% (Steppe et al. 2010). Possible reasons have been
402 attributed to species-specific differences of the empirical relation between sensor signal and SFD (Bush et
403 al. 2010, Sun et al. 2011), to the radial and circumferential variability of sap flux within the tree (Gebauer
404 et al. 2008), and to errors of the sensor location (Clearwater et al. 1999, Lu et al. 2004, Shin`ichi & Tadashi
405 2010). In any case, AC sensors in this study always detected a greater proportion of the real SFD than
406 wound-affected sensors, which allowed us to discern the wound effect as an intrinsic reason for the
407 underestimations of the TD method.

408
409 *4.2 Time frame for wound effect development*

410 The progressive wound development was reflected in the field data when wound-affected sensors installed
411 previously were compared to freshly installed sensors (Fig. 7). Differences between both sets of sensors
412 were largest within the first days, presumably due to the still absence of wound formation effects on the
413 most recently installed sensors. The magnitude of the differences falls, in fact, within the range of the
414 underestimations obtained in the lab experiment (Fig. 5). As the wounding reaction takes also place in
415 sensors installed more recently, SFD values get progressively closer until they (almost) converge. This may
416 mark the point when wounds have reached an asymptotic extension, so we can set the time frame for the
417 development of the wound bias to within the first two weeks after sensor installation. This period is
418 consistent with the time span reported in other studies for wound development, e.g. 14-21 days in Smith and
419 Allen (1996), 10-20 days in Swanson and Whitfield (1981), and 7 days after pruning in Sun et al. (2006).
420 Considering this time frame, wounds would have already reached the maturity in living tree stems around
421 all sets of sensors at the moment of tree cutting, which explains why no differences were found between the
422 sensors installed at different dates (spring, summer and fall sensors) in the lab validation experiment (Figs.
423 3 and 4).

424
425 This time frame should be, nonetheless, considered as a first orientation to demarcate potentially wound-
426 affected measurements. The rate of wound healing reaction might be influenced by several factors such as

427 tree phenological status, climatic conditions, age, growth rate, and sensor location (Liese & Dujesiefken
428 1996, Shortle et al. 1996, Dujesiefken et al. 1999, 2005, Sun et al. 2006, Moore et al. 2010). For example,
429 injuries compartmentalize faster in spring when the physiological mechanisms involved in the defense and
430 prevention of pathogens infections are fully active (Dujesiefken et al. 1999, 2005). The increased activity
431 of parenchyma in the early growing season may promote an improved wound reaction due to a better
432 formation of accessory substances (Dujesiefken et al. 2005). Higher temperatures may also facilitate a faster
433 wound reaction, increasing the efficiency of tissue compartmentalization (Moore et al. 2010). As a
434 mechanism involved in the wound healing reaction, tyloses formation occurred 30 to 45 days after injury in
435 winter but already within the first three days during the growing season (Shibata et al. 1981). According to
436 these factors, we would expect a less efficient and more extended wound reaction on injuries performed in
437 fall. In addition, young trees (Shortle et al. 1996) and, in general, fast growth rates (Dujesiefken et al. 2005)
438 are related to a faster injury repair. Tyloses development is also much slower in latewood and in the base
439 than in the apical trunk (Sun et al. 2006). In summary, wound development and hence the consequent
440 measurement errors may occur progressively along a variable time frame, which makes it difficult to predict
441 the magnitude of inaccuracies at a particular time. This highlights the necessity of a feasible procedure to
442 determine the time frame of wound development and the corrections needed to account for this relevant
443 source of error.

444

445 *4.3 Species-specific factors*

446 A greater impact of the wound effect on ring-porous species has been associated to their wider vessels,
447 which makes them more vulnerable to cavitation, microorganism invasion and less efficient in embolism
448 repair compared to diffuse-porous species (Liese & Dujesiefken 1996, Dujesiefken et al. 2005, Moore et al.
449 2010). When the sapwood is perforated for sensor installation, air comes into the damaged vessels through
450 the drilled hole due to the under-pressure existent inside the vessels. Bigger vessels of ring-porous species
451 are then more vulnerable to embolism and less capable to repair from cavitation (Sperry & Sullivan 1992,
452 Cochard & Tyree 1990). Air bubbles inside caved vessels reduce the heat transfer between water in the
453 xylem stream and the thermocouples of the sensor, leading to an apparent decline in the measured flux
454 (Moore et al. 2010). Moreover, vessels affected by irreversible cavitation suffer a series of anatomical
455 transformations that isolate the injured area, preventing pathogens colonization and further embolism
456 (Zimmermann 1979, Cochard & Tyree 1990, Dujesiefken et al. 1999). The accumulation of phenols and
457 pectic substances (gels), tyloses formation and thickening of cell walls can occlude partially or totally the
458 vessels, leading to an irreversible reduction in the hydraulic conductivity of the affected tissue
459 (Zimmermann 1979, Rioux et al. 1998, McElrone et al. 2010). Accordingly, sap flux density measured by
460 sensors surrounded by a wounded tissue is expected to be directly related to the extension of the caved
461 vessels and to the anatomical processes involved in the wound healing reaction. Several experiments using

462 either staining or microscopy have detected the wound formation beyond the point of the insertion probes
463 of heat pulse sensors and have found a direct relation between the extent of the physical and anatomical
464 transformations and sensor accuracy (Barrett et al. 1995). Vulnerability to irreversible cavitation and the
465 subsequent anatomical changes are also genetically determined (Biggs 1987, Saitoh et al. 1993). Impacts on
466 the accuracy of invasive sap-flow sensors due to the physical disruption encountered when drilling holes
467 and the subsequent wound anatomical transformation may then be strongly species dependent.

468
469 We could not find however consistent differences on the sap flux underestimations between oak (ring-
470 porous) and beech (diffuse-porous), but we cannot reject the hypothesis of species-specific differences on
471 the wound formation and subsequent measurement errors, since the experimental calibration of TD sensors
472 in oak has large uncertainties. The thin sapwood of one of the oak trees tested (0.54 cm depth) did not allow
473 a good comparison with gravimetric measurements despite the implementation of the Clearwater
474 correction (Clearwater et al. 1999), which has probably limited applicability if only one third of the sensor
475 length is in contact with conducting tissue. This shortcoming is reflected in the data by lower accuracy also
476 shown by AC sensors, low correlation coefficients with the reference gravimetric flux, larger intercepts
477 and higher estimation errors of the linear regressions parameters, similarly to what Bush et al. (2010)
478 observed for several ring-porous species. Further investigations are still needed in order to determine the
479 vulnerability to wound-related uncertainties of different species on the sap flux density measured with
480 invasive sensors.

481
482 *4.4 Recommendations to improve the accuracy of the TD method in the field*

483 The timing and magnitude of the wound reaction after sensor installation may be influenced by many factors
484 such as species, tree phenology, tree age, growth rate, climatic conditions, sensor size and location, and sap
485 flux rates (Shortle et al. 1996, Dujesiefken et al. 1999, 2005, Moore et al. 2010). It is therefore questionable
486 to apply a general empirical correction, which was derived in the laboratory such as presented here, to data
487 in the field. A laboratory calibration for each particular case is, on the other hand, very laborious and in
488 most cases not feasible due to logistic reasons or lack of infrastructure. We therefore present here an
489 alternative and feasible approach to establish the wound correction needed for a given species in any
490 particular forest stand.

491
492 The assumption underlying this approach and confirmed by data presented here, is that TD probes estimate
493 the correct SFD in the first few days after sensor installation and SFD estimates gradually decrease to biased,
494 lower values within a few weeks as wounds develop around inserted sensors. The effects of wound
495 formation on SFD estimates seem to change mainly in the first 2-4 weeks after installation (this study,
496 Swanson and Whitfield 1981, Smith and Allen 1996), period after which a further wound extension, if any,

497 does not add further bias on sensor measurements. In order to estimate the bias resulting from wounding,
498 we therefore recommend installing several sets of sensors sequentially in time instead of installing all
499 sensors at once. The detailed approach presented here counts on several steps:

500
501 1. A first set of sensors is installed in living trees early in the growing season at time t_1 , $SFD_1(t_1)$, where the
502 subscript 1 indicates the first set of sensors. These sensors will exhibit a wound effect and hence give biased,
503 low estimates of SFD after several weeks dt_1 : $SFD_1(t_1+dt_1)$. The number of replicate sensors to install per
504 sampling date depends on the variability of SFD within and between trees, which varies according to the
505 characteristics of the study site, sapwood depth and tree species (Oren et al. 1998, James et al. 2001,
506 Kumagai et al. 2005, Saveyn et al. 2008, Tsuruta et al. 2010, Kume et al. 2012). Ring-porous species with
507 narrow sapwood may need particularly larger number of replicate sensors, since errors associated to sensor
508 location may result in higher spatial variability (Oren et al. 1998, Clearwater et al. 1999). We recommend
509 performing a pilot study ahead to obtain an estimation of the SFD variability within and between trees and
510 estimate from this the required numbers of sensors (Quinn & Keough 2009).

511
512 2. A second set of sensors is then installed around 4 weeks later (at time t_2) in the same trees. These sensors
513 should record the correct SFD during the first few days, $SFD_2(t_2)$, and then exhibit slowly decreasing SFD
514 due to the wound effect, similar to the first sensor set.

515
516 3. The decreasing trend in SFD associated to the wound formation might well be overshadowed by
517 increasing or decreasing SFD due to changing environmental conditions. We therefore propose to use
518 potential transpiration (PT , Eq. 3) to select times with very similar meteorological conditions and hence
519 similar transpiration rates. Here we used a definition of potential, non-water limited transpiration for
520 selection because actual transpiration rates are not known or rather the target variable. This also takes into
521 account the correlation between the meteorological variables. Filtered SFD data should clearly reveal the
522 progressive drift on the second set of sensors, i.e. SFD_2 , when they are compared with the first sensors with
523 already fully developed wounds, i.e. SFD_1 .

524
525 4. Once wounds have also developed (at time t_2+dt_2) on the sensors installed more recently, a similar wound
526 effect will bias all SFD estimates, so that sap flux values from both sets of sensors will converge, i.e.
527 $SFD_1(t_2+dt_2) \sim SFD_2(t_2+dt_2)$. Nonetheless, final SFD estimates from different installations might still differ
528 due to the intrinsic spatial variability of sap flux. This may be especially true for narrow xylem trees, due to
529 slight variations in the length of the sensor inserted within the sapwood (Oren et al. 1998, Clearwater et al.
530 1999). In our case, there was a 7% offset in sap flux rates between spring [$SFD_1(t_2+dt_2)$] and summer
531 [$SFD_2(t_2+dt_2)$] installations (Fig. 7), which is well within observed sap flux variations between trees

532 (Köstner et al. 1998) or at different points in one tree (Saveyn et al. 2008). Calculating a correction factor
533 using the differences between both sensor sets could therefore introduce some systematic bias. We therefore
534 recommend using the first sensors only as a reference, wound-affected estimate to determine the time frame
535 (dt_2) of the wound reaction in the second set of sensors, i.e. when the asymptotic values from both sensor
536 sets “almost” converge or $SFD_2(t_2+dt_2)/SFD_1(t_2+dt_2) = \text{constant}$. The correction for the second sensors
537 should then be calculated using the ratios of the values at the beginning of installation (leaving apart
538 probably the first day for signal stabilization) to the asymptotic values after a few weeks, corrected for any
539 trend still present after filtering for potential transpiration. Therefore, the wound correction for the second
540 set of sensors is:

$$541 \quad c_2 = \frac{SFD_2(t_2)}{SFD_2(t_2 + dt_2)}$$

542 and, in order to correct sap flux estimates, SFD_2 will be multiplied by c_2 after the time point t_2+dt_2 .

543
544 5. The magnitude of wound bias and the time frame for wound development might be influenced by tree
545 phenology. We therefore recommend installing another, third set of sensors 4 weeks later (SFD_3). The
546 procedure of data selection and filtering is the same as for the second set of sensors (point 4) as well as the
547 calculation of the wound effect correction c_3 . Both, the first and second set of sensors can be used at this
548 point as wound-corrected estimates of SFD.

549
550 6. Finally, the mean \bar{c} of all correction factors from the second and third set of sensors will be used to correct
551 the SFD estimates from the set of sensors installed first (point 1), i.e.: $SFDc_1 = \bar{c} \times SFD_1$ after the time point
552 t_1+dt_1 , where \bar{c} is the average of all correction factors for each individual sensor of the second and third
553 installation.

554 555 **5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS**

556 Invasive sap flux density measurements can exhibit considerable underestimation of actual sap flux
557 densities. The causes of this measurement bias have not been identified for the thermal dissipation method
558 despite its widespread use. The study presented here identified wound healing in response to sensor insertion
559 within living tree stems as one of the most important sources of errors associated to the TD method.
560 Laboratory as well as field observations showed that the wound reaction led to a 21% to 47%
561 underestimation of sap flux density. This bias appeared progressively after sensor installation and reached
562 its maximum after about two weeks. The wound effect is likely influenced by climatic conditions, phenology
563 and tree species, amongst others, so that a general implementation of the observed correction factor is
564 probably not advisable. We propose instead an easy and practical approach to detect and account for the
565 wound effect in field observations: an initial installation of sap-flow sensors serves as reference to determine

566 the time frame of wound development. The influence of the wound reaction on sap flux density can then be
567 observed by selecting times with potentially similar sap flux ranges and comparing with the newly installed
568 sensors. Sap flux values can then be corrected by using the initial and the final converged values of each
569 sensor. This avoids biasing towards the specific sample of the reference installation.

570
571 This study represents a crucial step forward towards more accurate sap flux measurements with the thermal
572 dissipation method. The approach should, however, be independent of the observational method and be
573 applicable to other invasive sap-flow techniques as well. Further investigations might be warranted to better
574 understand the influence of the wound reaction on sap flux density measurements, including species-specific
575 wood anatomical transformations, their spatial extent and functional significance in relation to the accuracy
576 of TD sensors.

577
578 **6. FUNDING**
579 German Federal Ministry of Education and Research –INFLUINS– (03 IS 2001 A); European Union’s
580 Seventh Framework Program –Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions– and Ministry of Economy, Innovation,
581 Science and Employment of the Junta de Andalucía (291780 to S.M.J).

582
583 **7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**
584 We thank the members of the field-research groups of the Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, Jena
585 and the Chair of Bioclimatology of the University of Göttingen, the forestry office of Leinefelde for their
586 support with cutting the trees, and Dr Martina Mund for providing inventory data of the field site. Special
587 thanks goes to all members of the field research group of the UFZ Department Computational Hydrosystems
588 for their support during field and lab experiments, in particular to Martin Schrön, Hendrik Zöphel and
589 Sebastian Gimper.

590
591 **8. REFERENCES**
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742 **FIGURE LEGENDS:**

743
744 Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the sap flux calibration system used in the laboratory for testing the accuracy
745 of wound-affected and wound-free thermal dissipation sensors. Water is sucked through the stem segment
746 into the Erlenmeyer flask by the pump.

747
748 Figure 2: TD sensor response to stepwise changes in pumping pressure and hence flow rate through a cut
749 stem segment in European beech. The gray area highlights the various pressure-exposed conditions while
750 the white bands in-between are experimental interruptions due to emptying of the Erlenmeyer flask and
751 pump adjustments. SFD measured gravimetrically every 2 min (blue dots) is compared with TD sensors
752 (colored lines), installed at different dates on living tree stems. Lines represent arithmetic means of three
753 sensors and shaded areas represent the corresponding standard errors.

754
755 Figure 3: Comparison of SFD determined gravimetrically with TD sensors for the calibration tests
756 performed on beech segments. a) TD sensors installed 22 weeks before tree cutting (spring). b) Sensors
757 installed 11 weeks before cutting (summer). c) TD sensors installed 5 weeks earlier (fall). d) Sensors
758 installed after tree cutting (AC). Black circles are average values for one calibration step (34-108 sensor
759 readings averaged per data point), including standard errors of the TD sensors and the gravimetric
760 measurements. Black solid lines are linear fits while dashed lines are the 1:1 lines. Gray areas represent the
761 errors of the linear fits.

762
763 Figure 4: Comparison of SFD determined gravimetrically with TD sensors for the calibration tests
764 performed on oak segments. a) TD sensors installed 22 weeks before tree cutting (spring). b) Sensors
765 installed 11 weeks before cutting (summer). c) TD sensors installed 5 weeks earlier (fall). d) Sensors
766 installed after tree cutting (AC). Black circles are average values for one calibration step (34-108 sensor
767 readings averaged per data point), including standard errors of the TD sensors and the gravimetric
768 measurements. Black solid lines are linear fits while dashed lines are the 1:1 lines. Gray areas represent the
769 errors of the linear fits.

770
771 Figure 5: Comparison of SFD determined gravimetrically against all TD sensors installed 5, 11 and 22
772 weeks before tree cutting: a) European beech, b) sessile oak. Symbols are average values for one calibration
773 step, including standard errors of the TD sensors and the gravimetric measurements. Black solid lines are
774 linear fits while dashed lines are the 1:1 lines. Gray areas represent the errors of the linear fits.

775

776 Figure 6: Circumferential variability of SFD in cut stem segments of beech (left) and oak (right) under
777 maximal flow rates. The colored lines represent the locations of sensors of different wound ages around the
778 stems. The different intensity of blue along the rings represents the measured SFD by TD sensors at
779 maximum gravimetric flow. TD sensor measurements were linearly interpolated in this figure. The sensors
780 were installed in two rows and with at least 40 cm vertical distance between sensors. Overlapping in the
781 figure is the result of the projection on a single plane.

782

783 Figure 7: A) Time series of SFD measurements of beech in the field showing the progressive development
784 of the wound effect on freshly installed summer sensors. B) Percentage of the sap flux measured by freshly
785 installed summer sensors that is underestimated by old spring sensors. The dashed line shows the mean
786 underestimation by wound- affected sensors obtained in the lab calibration experiment.

787

788 Figure 8: Idealized diagram of the proposed approach to correct field SFD measurements for the wound
789 effect. Different line styles represent sap flux density values from different sets of sensors installed
790 consecutively in living trees. The diagram does not intend to represent real sap flux magnitudes or time
791 spans for wound effect development.